

Adsorption by Polar Precipitates. Part IV. Further Experiments with Silver Salts.

BY JNANENDRA NATH MUKHERJEE, JYOTI KANTA BASU AND
ASOKE MUKHERJEE.

The present work was undertaken in order to obtain further data on the adsorption of ions by insoluble polar precipitates with a view to elucidate the nature of the process. It has been shown by Mukherjee and Roy (this *Journal*, 1924, 1, 173), and by Mukherjee and Kundu (this *Journal*, 1926, 3, 335), that though the order of adsorbability of different ions by such precipitates on the whole runs parallel to the order of increasing solubilities of the salts composed of the ions in question and the oppositely charged ion in the precipitate, there are striking exceptions. They also mention that in general there is a strong adsorption of the constituent ions but here also there are exceptions. The above authors base their conclusions on electro-osmotic experiments which, they hold, give a better idea of the relative adsorption of the ions of the electrolyte by the surface. Analytical measurements, on the other hand, give the total adsorption in the surface layer. Beskley and Taylor (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 943), from analytical measurements of adsorption of silver salts by silver iodide, later came to the same conclusion as that of Mukherjee and Roy regarding exceptions to the above mentioned parallelism between solubility and adsorbability. The conclusions drawn from variations in electrical charges of such particles have a direct bearing on many analytical and related problems in chemistry. Hahn, Erbacher and Feichtinger (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 2014), in a very important paper, have recently shown the existence of a relationship between the adsorption of a radio-element by a polar precipitate and the electrical charge of the surface. Their work fully confirms the contention of Mukherjee (*Phil. Mag.*, 1923, 45, 821 ; cf. also Mukherjee and Roy, *loc. cit.*) that the precipitation rule of Paneth (*Phys. Zeit.*, 1914, 15, 924) is incomplete in so far as it does not take into consideration such types of adsorption of ions as would lead to a change in the charge of

the surface. Hahn and co-workers critically examine the observations of previous workers and their recent measurements and show that the well-known generalisations of Fajans and Paneth regarding the carrying down of radio-elements by precipitates, which have been of so great a service to radio-chemistry, require to be modified and altered so as to include the following new generalisation :—

“Ein Element wird aus beliebig grosser Verdünnung an einem Niederschlage (Adsorbens) dann adsorbiert, wenn dem Niederschlage eine dem Ladung des zu adsorbierenden Elementes entgegengesetzte Oberflächen—Ladung erteilt worden und die adsorbierte Verbindung in dem vorliegenden Lösungsmittel schwer löslich ist.” Hahn points out that the above generalisation is in full agreement with the work of Mukherjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 191), and of Michaelis and Dokan (*Koll. Zeit.*, 1925, 37, 67).

In the present paper we have used three insoluble silver salts, namely, the chloride, bromide and iodide as adsorbent and solutions of silver and of sodium salts. The experiments with silver salts enable us to compare our results with those from the analytical measurements of Taylor and Beekley. Such a comparison has a good deal of theoretical interest and is likely to throw light on the nature of the adsorption of ions.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Three apparatus were set up for the three diaphragms. The arrangement described in previous papers (*loc. cit.*) was used. Every experiment was carried out under exactly similar conditions.

Preparation of the insoluble silver salts.

(i) *Silver Iodide*.—The procedure described by Beekley and Taylor (*loc. cit.*) has been rigidly followed.

(ii) *Silver Bromide*.—As with the iodide. Washing was continued till the precipitate, on being kept in contact with conductivity water for a week, did not change the p_x to any appreciable extent. The particles were fairly big in size and had well defined crystalline structure. The salt, however, was not insensitive to light and so all the experiments were carried out in presence of light from a lamp with a ruby glass shield.

(iii) *Silver Chloride*.—Decinormal solutions of pure recrystallised potassium chloride and silver nitrate were prepared and mixed in darkness and allowed to settle for 48 hours. Fifty c. c. of a ten per cent. solution of ammonia were subsequently added to the colloidal mixture when the whole of the silver salt at once came down as heavy big particles ; washing was continued as above.

Three preparations of the iodide and two of the bromide did not show any change in the rate of movement of the bubble using conductivity water. This shows that these samples are reproducible so far as the rate of the movement is concerned (*cf.* Mukherjee and Kundu (*loc. cit.*) who found a difference).

Preparation of the Electrolytes.

(i) *Silver Nitrate*.—Merck's Reagent quality was recrystallised from conductivity water.

(ii) *Silver Nitrite*.—precipitated from pure recrystallised silver nitrate and sodium nitrite was washed free from the nitrate with water. It was next washed with absolute alcohol followed by ether. The latter was carefully evaporated and the sample was kept in an amber coloured vacuum desiccator. The whole operation was carried out in a dark room in presence of dim ruby lamp.

(iii) *Silver Acetate*.—precipitated from concentrated solutions of the respective recrystallised salts. The precipitate was redissolved in warm water, recrystallised and dried in an amber coloured vacuum desiccator.

(iv & v) *Silver Bromate and Benzoate*.—As above.

(vi-x) *Sodium salts* of arsenious, hydrobromic, sulphocyanic, acetic and salicylic acids were prepared by recrystallising Merck's 'reagent' samples.

Diaphragm.

The charge measurements were carried out at four different dilutions for each electrolyte, the concentration being N/1000, N/5000, N/10,000 and N/20,000. About 5 g. of the adsorbent material was washed several times with the solution in question and allowed to remain for 24 hours in a Jena glass stoppered bottle and transferred to the U-tube, and left undisturbed for 2 hours. The U-tube was dipped in a constant temperature bath, Four direct

and four reverse readings (for three minutes each) were taken. The mean of these are tabulated. The results are reproducible within 4 per cent.

The measurements of the charge in the case of bromide and chloride were carried out in a dark room with no light other than that of a photographic ruby lamp.

Results.

TABLE I.

Silver Iodide.

Conc.	AgNO ₃	AgNO ₂	Ag Acet.	AgBrO ₂	Ag Benzoate.
N/0·0	-2·5	-2·5	-2·5	-2·5	-2·5
N/20,000	7·2	7·1	7·2	6·9	6·0
N/10,000	10·2	8·7	8·85	7·75	7·8
N/5,000	12·3	9·4	9·8	10·2	8·9
N/1,000	13·5	10·9	12·1	13·2	9·7

TABLE II.

Silver Bromide.

Conc.					
N/0·0	-3·1	-3·1	-3·1	-3·1	-3·1
N/20,000	8·0	7·6	8·5	7·4	7·5
N/10,000	10·1	8·2	8·4 (?)	8·0	8·0
N/5,000	12·5	10·1	10·6	10·75	10·0
N/1,000	14·7	11·0	14·65	14·0	10·1

TABLE III.

Silver Iodide.

Conc.	Na Arsenite.	NaBr.	NaSCN.	Na Acetate.	Na Salicylate.
N/0 0	-2·5	-2·5	-2·5	-2·5	-2·5
N/20 000	-4·2	-6·0	-12·3	-7·6	-8·0
N/10,000	-5·0	-6·5	-13·8	-9·1	-10·0
N/5,000	-7·2	-6·8	-20·0	-11·5	-12·8
N/1,000	-16·3	-7·2	-21·9	-15·0	-15·4

(?) 9·4 probably.

TABLE IV.

Silver Bromide.

Conc.	Na Arsenite	NaBr	NaSCN	Na Acetate	Na Salicylate
N/0.0	-8.1	-8.1	-8.1	-8.1	-8.1
N/20,000	-4.0	-4.2	-13.0	-4.2	-6.0
N/10,000	-7.3	-4.8	-19.2	-7.5	-8.3
N/5,000	-9.3	5.0	-21.4	-9.6	-11.0
N/1,000	-17.4	-9.7	-26.5	-16.8	-17.0

TABLE V.

Silver Chloride.

Conc.					
N/0.0	...	...	-4.3	-4.3	-4.3
N/20,000	...	...	-12.4	-5.1	-6.7
N/10,000	...	...	-18.26	-7.2	-8.3
N/5,000	...	...	-22.9	-9.45	-11.8
N/1,000	...	...	-27.3	-13.9	-15.2

For purposes of comparison we give below the solubilities of silver salts.

TABLE VI.

Solubility of Silver Salts.

	Thiocyanate.	Bromide.	Arsenite.	Salicylate.
Solubility in millimols per g. H ₂ O	20°C 0.0000008*	20°C 0.0000004*	20°C 0.00008*	15°C 0.2089*
	Bromate.	Benzoate.	Nitrite.	Acetate.
Solubility in millimols per g. H ₂ O	20°C 0.006*	25°C 0.0114†	25°C 0.0259†	20°C 0.06*
				Nitrate. 4*

* Landolt and Bornstein's Tables.

† Beekley and Taylor (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 29, 943).

Discussion.

Considering the adsorption of ions from the silver solutions we find in each case a rise in the positive charge, the originally negative charge of the precipitate becoming positive. The strong adsorption of silver ions observed previously is thus confirmed. As a result of the anion adsorption, the charges will be different. The adsorption of the anions is directly comparable as they are all univalent. The relative order of the adsorption of the anions remain the same throughout the range of concentration studied with the exception of the bromate and is the same for both the iodide and the bromide as adsorbents namely: benzoate > nitrite > acetate > nitrate. The bromate comes near the acetate at the higher concentrations though it shows greater relative adsorption at the lower concentrations. Its adsorption is throughout less than that of the benzoate ion. The order of increasing solubilities is bromate > benzoate > nitrite > acetate > nitrate. Excepting the bromate the two series are identical showing that the intensity of adsorption is related to solubility. Beekley and Taylor working with silver iodide as adsorbent find a different order of adsorbabilities: benzoate > acetate > nitrite > bromate > nitrate. It is possible that the analytical measurements of Beekley and Taylor do not give a correct idea of the relative adsorption of ions. In the present instance we are dealing mainly with a primary adsorption of silver ions and comparing equivalent concentrations of the different silver salts, the amounts of silver ions adsorbed per unit area of the same adsorbent should be identical if we assume that the anions are not primarily adsorbed. The anions from silver salts are possibly adsorbed in two ways: (a) primary adsorption on account of the affinity of the atoms on the surface; (b) 'electrical' adsorption. The picture that we can form of the surface layer in contact with the solutions of the silver salts is that near each halide ion on the surface silver ions are primarily adsorbed, and near each silver ion anions are primarily adsorbed. In the case of such polar precipitates it is difficult to distinguish between primary and electrical adsorption excepting that in the case of primary adsorptions the ion is adsorbed in an unhydrated state and in the electrical adsorption a layer of solvent molecules probably intervenes between ions of opposite charge. Thus ultimate distribution of the different ions on the surface will be determined by the primary adsorption of the two ions as also by

the electrical adsorption of the two ions. In the present case we may neglect the 'electrical' adsorption of the silver ions because of the marked positive charge of the surface which shows that the 'fixed' layer on the surface always contains an excess of silver ions. The mobile sheet will contain an excess of the anions, and, if there be no exchange between anions in the solid and those in the liquid, from analytical measurements we ought to find an equivalent adsorption of both ions, mainly determined by the adsorption of the silver ions. The differences in the comparatively smaller amounts of adsorption of the anions will therefore be masked by the stronger adsorption of the silver ions, and if we consider the difficulties of correctly estimating small amounts of adsorption the discrepancy between the order of adsorption obtained by ourselves and that of Beekley and Taylor may be attributed in part to these factors. From their data we notice that the difference in the adsorption of nitrite and acetate at the higher concentration is such as to exclude this possibility. We have observed that the nitrite and the acetate have nearly the same adsorbability with the iodide as adsorbent and that the difference between their adsorption is greater when the bromide is the adsorbent. We would however mention that the adsorption experiments of Beekley and Taylor with acetate and nitrite were performed with two different samples of the precipitate possibly of different adsorbing capacities.

The stronger adsorption of the silver salts found by the above authors and by us is in agreement with the observation of Mukherjee and Kundu with silver iodide that the iodine ions are comparatively weakly adsorbed compared to that of the other constituent ion.

With the sodium salts we again observe that the order of adsorption of the anions is the same with the iodide, bromide and chloride as adsorbents. Arsenite behaves as the bromate does in the case of silver salts. The order of adsorption of these anions is thiocyanate > arsenite > salicylate > acetate > bromide. The order of increasing solubilities is thiocyanate > bromide > arsenite > salicylate > acetate. The comparatively weak adsorption of both the iodine and the bromine ions strengthens our conclusion regarding the weakness of adsorption of the constituent halide ions. The adsorptions of the nitrate ion and the chloride ion by silver iodide precipitates are comparable as appears from the work of Mukherjee and Kundu and that of Taylor and Beekley.

If we express the relative adsorption of the anions taking the data with silver acetate and sodium acetate as the basis of comparison we arrive at the following order of decreasing adsorption of anions:—

Thiocyanate > arsenite (?) > salicylate (?) > benzoate > nitrite > acetate > bromate (?) > nitrate > bromide (?), whereas the order of increasing solubilities is thiocyanate > bromide > arsenite > salicylate > bromate > benzoate > nitrite > acetate > nitrate.

Summary and Conclusion.

(1) The chloride, bromide and iodide of silver have negative charges in contact with water.

(2) The charge is reversed at a low dilution of silver salts.

(3) The order of adsorption of anions in silver salts by electro-osmotic method is benzoate > nitrite > acetate > nitrate.

Excepting the bromate this order is identical with the order of increasing solubility.

This order differs from the order of adsorption of these salts by silver iodide observed by Beekley and Taylor with respect to the position of acetate and bromate ions.

From experiment with sodium salts the following order of adsorption of anions is obtained: thiocyanate > arsenite > salicylate > acetate > bromide, which is the same as the order of increasing solubilities; the bromide forms an exception.